

Safety-aware decision making for collaborative robotics: An integrated approach

Marco Faroni, Christian Cella, Andrea M. Zanchettin, Paolo Rocco

Abstract—We propose an integrated approach to human-aware decision-making in manufacturing scenarios. The framework is motivated by the need to embed safety awareness into robot decision-making to minimize avoidable safety stops and reduce inefficiencies owed to human-robot interference. We discuss when these methodologies are effective and illustrate the working principle with a simulated example.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaboration between humans and robots requires a paradigm change in robots’ perception, reasoning, and action. Speaking of decision-making, this shift encompasses different levels of abstraction and reactivity. For example, the system should find a suitable sequence of operations (task planning) [1], assign them to the agents (task assignment) [2], and schedule their execution (scheduling) [3]. At runtime, the execution of the operations should be adapted to the human and robot’s state (motion planning and replanning) [4]. Existing works usually address a single aspect at a time.

Manufacturing-oriented approaches usually aim to find a good trade-off between safety and efficiency. Such a safety-vs.-efficiency compromise is owed to the implementation of safety specifications in human-robot collaboration. For example, the ISO-TS/15066 [5] provides rules to slow down the robot when the human worker is in the robot’s proximity. Practical implementations of the ISO-TS/15066 are conservative and may jeopardize the effectiveness of the interaction (e.g., by stopping the robot as soon as the human enters the shared space). New methods to avoid unnecessary efficiency losses while being compliant with safety standards are key to deploying effective collaborative robots.

We claim that the safety-v.-efficiency trade-off can be overcome by making the robot’s decision-making aware of safety rules that govern the production process. We also claim that such a safety-aware approach should consistently encompass all decision-making layers. For example, if the local motion planner is optimized to avoid humans but the task order is such that the robot and the operator often need to access the same area, the benefits of the former are soon jeopardized. For this reason, we propose an integrated approach that tackles the safety-aware decision-making problem from its many facets, including:

- A formalization of the HRC process that considers synergies between human and robot tasks so that the

This study was partially carried out within the MICS (Made in Italy – Circular and Sustainable) Extended Partnership and received funding from Next-Generation EU (Italian PNRR – M4 C2, Invest 1.3 – D.D. 1551.11-10-2022, PE00000004). CUP MICS D43C22003120001.

The authors are with Politecnico di Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32. Milano (Italy) marco.faroni@polimi.it

Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed framework.

task planning and scheduling is aware of positive or negative couplings between simultaneous tasks.

- A safety-aware motion planner leveraging safety rules directly derived from ISO-TS/15066 to optimize the robot motion according to the operator’s state.
- A pre-deployment approach to optimize the layout design of the collaborative cell according to safety and efficiency criteria by using a human digital twin to simulate the worker’s behavior beforehand.

Please note that this is a summary of the late and current research of the authors. Part of the results described in this abstract are adapted from [6]–[10].

II. APPROACH

The proposed framework is sketched in Figure 1. Each layer’s functionality is detailed as follows.

1) *Synergy-based task planning and scheduling*: We consider a set of human and robot agents tasked with a production process. We formulate the task planning and scheduling problem as an optimization problem that minimizes the expected process duration [7]. To consider the coupling between simultaneous tasks, we define a synergy index, $s_{i,j}$, accounting for how the i th robot task duration depends on the j th human concurrent task. E.g., if the robot and the human access the same area, the robot will slow down, then $s_{i,j} > 1$. We use machine learning algorithms to estimate the synergy indices and the average duration of the tasks from a set of executions and a MILP formulation to solve the resulting optimization problem [8].

2) *Safety-aware path planning and re-planning*: We solve an optimal motion planning problem by minimizing the path execution time, including safety speed reductions caused by

human proximity. To do so, we encode the expected speed reduction—as defined in ISO-TS/15066—into a cost function to minimize the expected execution time, instead of a trade-off of human-robot distance and path length and use it in an RRT*-based planner [6] and an online path re-planner [9].

3) *Reactive safety-aware speed modulation*: An additional way to avoid unnecessary robot slowdowns is to implement a continuous modulation of the robot speed in such a way as to comply with ISO-TS/15066. To do so, we derive the maximum robot speed allowed by the safety specification according to the robot’s state and the human real-time position (tracked by a vision system). Please note that this is not a safety module *per se* because of the lack of safety-certified vision-based human tracking systems. Currently, this module aims to avoid unnecessary safety stops and slowdowns. However, it will likely be integrated into safety modules when the perception technology is mature enough to achieve safety certification.

4) *Pre-deployment optimization of collaborative cells*: We aim to optimize the cell layout during the pre-deployment design through Bayesian Optimization. Our goal is to optimize the position of the robot, fixtures, tools, and pallets to optimize the collaborative process [10]. The approach consists of a human digital twin simulating human behaviors and a high-dimensional Bayesian Optimization algorithm seeking the best cell configuration. The optimized layout will serve as a guideline for the deployment of the cell.

III. EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

We implemented our approach in several manufacturing case studies and demonstrated its efficacy in reducing execution times and improving human comfort. For example, consider the scenario in Fig. 2, where the robot and the human are tasked with pick&places. The Task Planner&Scheduler decides who to assign each pick&place to and the order of execution. This choice is based on the synergies estimated from a dataset of executions. For example, the synergy learning spots that simultaneous pick&places of blue cubes are disadvantageous because they require the robot and the human to access the same area at the same time.

Once the order and assignment of the actions are carried out, the motion planner is in charge of finding the optimal path minimizing the actual execution times (including possible safety slowdowns). The optimal path is sent to the robot and the speed modulation module adapts the velocity profile in such a way as to avoid safety stops. More complex scenarios and real experiments can be found in [6], [7].

When dealing with industrial scenarios, we need to understand when the advantages of the proposed solution justify the technological complexity of the solution. We identified two major factors: the frequency of HR interactions and the availability of domain-dependent knowledge. This analysis can be summarized as in Fig. 3: as we go up in the level of abstraction, we need more domain-related knowledge to be available (e.g., expected tasks duration and synergy, human motion prediction). On the other hand, simpler technologies are often enough when the frequency of interaction is low.

Fig. 2: Example scenario of a simulated HRC application.

Fig. 3: Suitability of the different decision-making paradigms according to the frequency of HRC and availability of domain-dependent knowledge.

We are currently investigating these aspects to evaluate such relations quantitatively.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

We described an integrated approach to safety-aware decision-making in collaborative robotics. The common thread of the approach is that each level is aware of safety rules that govern the robot’s behavior and avoids unnecessary stops and interference between the robot and the human.

Current works are focusing on how to include quantitative ergonomics factors in the decision-making algorithm.

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